

**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE,
ACCEPTABILITY AND UPTAKE OF
CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG
FEMALE LECTURERS AT THE UNIVERSITY
OF BENIN**

ABSTRACT

Background: Cervical cancer is a disease of public health interest because it is easily preventable. It is the fourth most common cancer in women and the second most common gynecological cancer worldwide. Fortunately, screening for premalignant lesions can help prevent this cancer.

Objectives: This study was undertaken to assess the knowledge, attitude and acceptability of cervical cancer screening among female lecturers of the University of Benin.

Methodology: This study was a descriptive cross-sectional survey of 370 female lecturers at University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria, using a self-administered structured questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 software. Chi-squared test was used to determine association between respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and their level of acceptability of cervical cancer screening as well as their knowledge of cervical cancer and cervical cancer screening. Statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Three hundred and seventy respondents participated in this study with a mean age of 41.1 ± 7.2 years. The respondents exhibited poor knowledge of cervical cancer and cervical cancer screening (46.8%). There was generally very satisfactory attitude towards cervical cancer screening (96.2%), and a good level of acceptability of cervical cancer screening (78.4%).

Conclusion: Although almost all the female lecturers in the University of Benin were aware of cervical cancer screening, only about half of them had good overall knowledge about cervical cancer and its screening.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Acceptability, Cervical cancer, Screening

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 . BACKGROUND

Cervical cancer is a disease of public health interest because it is easily preventable.¹ It usually occurs in the fifth to sixth decade of life and at a mean age of 54 years.² Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer in women, and the second most common gynecological cancer worldwide, after breast cancer.³

In 2018, an estimated 570 000 women were diagnosed with cervical cancer worldwide and about 311 000 women died from the disease and every 2 minutes a woman dies from cervical cancer.^{3,4} Eighty-four percent of these new cases and between 87% and 90% of the deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) like Brazil, Nigeria, South Africa.⁵

Africa has the highest incidence and mortality rates of cervical cancer among other regions of the world. The rates are high in the Southern Africa countries with Swaziland having the highest incidence rate; followed by Eastern Africa with Malawi having the highest rate of death followed by Zimbabwe; and Western Africa, with Guinea, Burkina Faso, and Mali taking the lead in that order.⁶

The incidence of cervical cancer in Nigeria is about 250 in 100,000 women.⁷ Nigeria has a population of 50.33 million women of age 15 years and above who are at risk of developing cervical cancer. Current estimates indicate that every year 14,943 women are diagnosed with

cervical cancer and 10,403 die from the disease in Nigeria. Cervical cancer ranks as the 2nd most frequent cancer among women in Nigeria accounting for 14.8% of all cancer deaths in Nigeria.^{8,9}

Common risk factors associated with cervical cancer include, sexually transmitted diseases like the Human Papilloma Virus, HIV, Herpes; sexual factors like early coitarche, multiparity, oral contraceptives, multiple sexual partners, and females whose consorts have multiple sexual partners; behavioral factors like smoking and obesity; host factors like genetic predisposition; and low socioeconomic class.¹⁰

The most important risk factor however is the Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) as it is responsible for virtually all cervical cancers. HPV is a sexually transmitted disease, therefore it is largely preventable. HPV has over 100 subtypes but the oncogenic/high-risk HPV subtypes (e.g., HPV-16 and HPV-18) are responsible for most cervical cancers and pre-cancers. Persistent oncogenic HPV infection is the strongest risk factor for development of HPV-associated pre-cancers and cancers, cervical cancer being the commonest.¹¹

Common signs and symptoms of cervical cancer include post-coital bleeding, intermenstrual bleeding, post-menopausal bleeding, foul-smelling and blood-stained vaginal discharge, pain during sex, contact bleeding.¹² Cervical cancer is a potentially preventable disease if appropriate screening and prophylactic strategies are employed. Early diagnosis and treatment of Cervical Cancer in women are crucial for reducing mortality rates. Fortunately, cervical cancer has a long premalignant period that provides an opportunity for screening and treatment before it becomes invasive cervical cancer.¹³

Three different types of screening tests are currently recommended by the WHO. They include; HPV DNA testing for high-risk HPV types; Visual inspection with Acetic Acid (VIA); Conventional Papanicolaou test (Pap test) and liquid-based cytology (LBC).¹⁴ Population-based screening with Papanicolaou (Pap) smear or cytology is the most widely used secondary preventive measure for Cervical Cancer that leads to a high-cure rate among Cervical Cancer patients.¹⁰ It is estimated that screening at 3-year interval for women aged 35-64 years can reduce the incidence of invasive cancer by over 90%.²

The incidence of cervical cancer is decreasing in developed countries because of availability of well-organized cervical screening programs.^{2,10} Cervical cancer used to be the leading cause of cancer death for women in the United States of America. However, in the past 40 years, the number of cases of cervical cancer and the number of deaths from cervical cancer have decreased significantly. This decline is as a result screening using Pap Smear tests, which can detect cervical pre-cancerous cells before it turns into carcinoma in situ.¹⁵

In 2008, 11/100,000 women in the United States were diagnosed with cervical cancer while 3/100,000 women died from cervical cancer.¹⁶ However, the incidence of cervical cancer continues to rise in developing countries.^{2,10} The high burden of cervical cancer in developing countries, like Nigeria, is due both to a high prevalence of HPV infection and the lack of effective cervical cancer screening programs.¹⁷ In cases where effective screening programs are available, poor knowledge and negative health-seeking behavior of the populace have led to poor utilization of such services.¹⁰ An important strategy towards the reduction of the incidence and mortality associated with cervical cancer is by increasing the screening rate of women that have not screened or those that screen infrequently.¹⁸

Knowledge about cancer of the cervix and its screening is important in screening uptake. Women with low levels of knowledge about cervical cancer and its prevention are less likely to access screening services.^{20,21,22} The HPV vaccine also contributes to the reducing incidence of cervical cancer. Countries that have achieved high vaccination coverage have observed declines of 73–85% in vaccine-type HPV prevalence among young women, less than 10 years after implementation of HPV vaccination.²³ There are currently 3 HPV vaccines and they include the 9-valent HPV vaccine (Gardasil[®] 9, 9vHPV); the quadrivalent HPV vaccine (Gardasil[®], 4vHPV); and the bivalent HPV vaccine (Cervarix[®], 2vHPV) and they have been licensed by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA).²² Vaccination and screening offer the best chance of preventing cervical cancer and detecting it early when treatment can be most successful. Screening can also prevent most cervical cancers by finding abnormal cervical cell changes (pre-cancers) so that they can be treated before they have a chance to turn into cervical cancer.²⁴

1.2 . STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In Nigeria, accessibility to cervical cancer screening services is poor. Screening services are mostly found in tertiary and secondary health facilities and the cost of screening is as high as ten thousand naira (20 USD) in these facilities.²⁵ About 40%(83 million) of Nigeria’s population live below the poverty line of 1 dollar per day.²⁶ Nigeria has a healthcare system that is largely dependent on out-of-pocket expenditure, making the cost of screening unaffordable to most women in the population.²⁷

Uptake of screening is reportedly low in Nigeria,²⁸ and a study carried out in a slum in Okada, a community in Edo state, Southern Nigeria, showed that none of the women living in the community had been screened for cervical cancer.²⁹ Several studies have documented reasons for

the poor uptake of cervical cancer screening and some of these reasons include financial constraint, inadequate information about cervical cancer screening, lack or inaccessibility of screening facilities, and logistic and cultural obstacles to screening, which ultimately result in late diagnosis and poor prognosis.^{30,31}

Delayed diagnosis of cervical cancer increases the proportion of cervical cancer cases presenting in an advanced stage and also leads to treatment failure, therefore, delay in diagnosis of cervical cancer connotes a poor prognosis and adversely impacts the quality of life of the patients. Poor uptake of screening also directly accounts for the increasing burden and increasing mortality of cervical cancer in developing countries, compared to developed countries.³²

A mother's death is largely viewed as a tragedy that has immediate and long-term emotional, psychological, economic effects on surviving children, households, and communities. Some of these effects include financial instability resulting from loss of income, thus limiting access to basic necessities such as food, shelter and health care. This predisposes surviving children, especially those under the age of 5 to malnutrition, childhood infections and increased mortality. Studies have shown that children whose mothers have died are more likely to leave school, and for surviving children who are girls, the only viable options were early marriage and early motherhood. Therefore, the negative impact of a mother's death due to cervical cancer cannot be overemphasized.^{33,34,35}

Women diagnosed with cervical cancer suffer myriads of psychological challenges. Some of these challenges include side effects of treatment like fatigue, urinary incontinence, loss of appetite. The pungent smell of the liquid discharge caused by the disease is also another major challenge and it can adversely affect the social interactions of these women. A study that interviewed women with

cervical cancer showed that many of them felt ashamed to be around people during the times they experienced these side effects.³⁶

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

Cervical cancer is still a major public health problem affecting middle-aged women, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. An increase in HPV-based screening has potential to make cervical cancer a rare disease in the foreseeable future. This study will help shape the initiative to eliminate cervical cancer as a major public health problem and guide the government and other health organizations in making decisions towards the implementation of cervical cancer screening programs.

Several reasons behind the poor uptake of cervical cancer screening in developing countries have been highlighted in the statement of the problem. However, over time, research in this field has made it clear that low uptake of cervical cancer screening is not only due to the reasons aforementioned but is also equally due a general behavior of neglect on the part of health care providers. Therefore, it is imperative to bring about a change in the attitude of the health care providers regarding importance of cervical cancer screening and this study will help in bringing about this change. This research will also add to the existing body of knowledge more reasons behind the low uptake of screening and identify possible solutions.

Research has shown that most cases of cervical cancer in low- and middle-income countries are usually diagnosed in advanced stages and this connotes a poor prognosis. This study will increase awareness of cervical cancer screening, promote early presentation and reduce the mortality of the disease. There is not enough literature on the attitude and acceptability of cervical cancer screening

among middle to upper class women, therefore this study will add to the existing body of knowledge

1.4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the knowledge of cervical screening among the University of Benin female lecturers?
2. What is the level of acceptability of cervical cancer screening among the University of Benin female lecturers?

1.5. GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To assess the knowledge, attitude and acceptability of cervical cancer screening among female lecturers of the University of Benin.

1.6 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the knowledge of cervical cancer screening among female lecturers in the University of Benin.
2. To determine the attitude of female lecturers in the University of Benin towards cervical cancer screening.
3. To determine the level of uptake and acceptability of cervical cancer screening among female lecturers of the University of Benin.
4. To identify the factors that influence cervical cancer screening among female lecturers of the University of Benin.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 KNOWLEDGE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING.

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted involving 235 consenting women of reproductive age (15-49 years) attending immunization clinic at Central Hospital Benin City. The study was conducted to assess the knowledge and screening practices of cervical cancer among women of reproductive age in Benin City. One hundred and thirteen (48.1%) of the women studied were aware of cervical cancer with 57(50.4%) having good knowledge of cervical cancer. In relation to knowledge on cervical cancer, primary level of education was the only significant predictor identified. In relation to practice of cervical cancer screening, 31(27.4%) of the respondents studied had been previously screened for cervical cancer while 82 (72.6%) had not. Finally, in relation to factors associated with cervical cancer screening practices, it was identified that employment status, marital status and parity were the only significant factors associated with cervical cancer screening practices among respondents while religion, age of respondents, educational status and knowledge of cervical cancer were not significant. The limitation of this study is that it was done only in an urban area and did not take into cognizance those living in rural areas.³⁷

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was adopted to explore the knowledge, attitude and perception of women attending antenatal clinic on cervical cancer screening in Owerri West Local Government Area of Imo State, southeastern Nigeria. Four (4) primary healthcare in the area, namely Orogwe, Obinze and Ihiagwa 1 and 2, were randomly selected for the study. These primary healthcare centers had a total number of women at the reproductive age as 4643, while a total of 547 visited these primary healthcare facilities within the period of study. The result showed that there was a high level of awareness (68.8%) of cervical cancer screening. The majority of women (122 (52.8%)) received this information from friends. Although the majority of the participants had heard about the screening, few of them had basic information on the cause of the disease 44 (19%), prevention 32 (13.9%), risk factors 48 (20.8%) and treatment (23.4%) of the disease. The study revealed strong influence of age and level of education on awareness of cervical cancer screening. Moreover, educational status had a significant positive influence on the cause of cervical cancer, with a higher proportion of participants with post-secondary education. The strength of this study is that the abstract offered a clear overview of the study including the research problem, sample, methodology, findings and recommendations ³⁸

A descriptive community based cross-sectional study was carried out in Gondar town, Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia. The study populations were all reproductive age group women who were living in four randomly selected kebeles of Gondar town. In this study, it was found that more than half, 501 (65.1%) of the participants had heard about cervical cancer. Of those who had heard about cervical cancer, the largest number, 206 (41.1%) had heard from mass media. This study revealed that only 153 (19.87%) of the participants had good knowledge regarding cervical cancer and its prevention. Regarding screening tests, of the 501 participants who had heard about cervical cancer, only 107 (21.4%) of them said they had heard about the Pap smear test. The

limitation of this study is that it was limited to Gondar town only due to constraints of time and funds. It would have been better if the rural women were included and differences in knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer were assessed among the two groups.³⁹

A cross-sectional and population-based study was conducted with 386 Turkish women aged 18-65 years old in Edirne to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice about cervical cancer screening. It was determined that 42.8% of women know that it is necessary to administer regular pap smear test to prevent cervical cancer. Women who had never been administered pap-smear test said they did not have knowledge about it (42.7%). The limitation of this study is that the findings were based on self-report as it was not possible to validate claims made by respondents in the course of questionnaire administration.⁴⁰

2.2 ATTITUDE TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING.

A comparative cross-sectional study was undertaken to assess the of knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer and its screening among clinical students in southern Nigeria. There were 100 female clinical nursing students in Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH) and all were selected for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 female clinical students from UBTH. The mean age of respondents in DELSUTH was 24.2 ± 2.6 years, compared to 23.2 ± 2.9 years for UBTH. Eighty-six percent (86%) in DELSUTH compared to 79% in UBTH had positive attitude towards cervical cancer screening.

Fourteen percent (14.0%) of the respondents in DELSUTH had negative attitude towards cervical cancer screening compared to 21.0% in UBTH. Among the respondents who had negative attitude to cervical cancer screening; a higher proportion 5.0% in DELSUTH, compared to 2.0% in UBTH

claimed that they did not go for screening because the procedure was embarrassing to them. The limitation of this study is that it was purposive in nature and prone to bias, as findings from this study are not guaranteed to be representative enough and not generalizable because it was conducted on a small sample size that was restricted to 200 clinical students.⁴¹

A descriptive cross-sectional, questionnaire-based study was carried out to assess the knowledge, attitude and utilization of cervical cancer screening among market women, aged 15 years and above, in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. A total of 260 women were administered with questionnaires. Although their knowledge of symptoms of cervical cancer was fair, their attitude towards cervical cancer screening was poor (19.6%). Some patients would go to seek care after noticing symptoms in hospitals (72.1%), traditional healers (10.5%), religious healers (7.4%), while 10.1% would not go anywhere. Respondents identified fear of outcome of screening, lack of information and public awareness, lack of health worker request, high cost of screening and lack of personnel at the screening centers as the reasons why people do not patronize cervical screening. The limitation of this study is that the abstract did not offer a clear overview of the research problem, sampling technique, and recommendations.⁴²

A cross-sectional study was conducted on female healthcare professionals at King Fahd Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards cervical cancer and screening amongst female healthcare professionals. The study population was stratified according to their professions into three groups: physicians, nurses, and allied healthcare workers. The majority of the study participants were nurses (66.1%) and the mean age of the participants was 34.7 years. A total of 261 (66.1%) respondents were nurses, 63 (16.0%) respondents were physicians, and the remaining 71 (18.0%) respondents included pharmacists, dieticians,

technicians, health educators, physiotherapists, and therapists. A total of 343 (86.8%) participants believed that Pap smear test is a useful test for the detection of cervical cancer and 103 (26.2%) participants had undergone Pap smear testing. More than three-fourths of the participants (84.8%) disagreed with the statement “screening helps in prevention of carcinoma of the cervix”. Overall, only 15 (3.8%) respondents agreed that they would have screening done if it was free and caused no harm. The strength of this study is that the questionnaire was developed from previously published studies after an in-depth literature review and then validated through experts in research methodology, obstetrics and gynecology, and oncology and they all confirmed the validity of the questionnaire before the study.⁴³

2.3 ACCEPTABILITY OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

A descriptive cross-sectional study was done in in University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria, to ascertain the knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer screening among female undergraduate residing in the halls of residence of the university of Benin Ugbowo campus. A sample of 355 was chosen from a target population of 3180. The study revealed that 236 (66.6%) of the respondents were unwilling to take the cervical cancer screening, while a comparatively smaller proportion 119 (33.4%) were willing to take the screening. The limitation of this study is that it involves only women in their reproductive age group, which will not give a detailed result compared to when postmenopausal women were included.⁴⁴

A cross-sectional survey was conducted at the HIV treatment center, Nigerian Institute of Medical Research (NIMR), Lagos. NIMR is the apex medical research institution in Nigeria charged with the responsibility to conduct research into disease of public health importance in the Country. The participants of the study were adult females aged 18 years and older seen at the center for their

monthly antiretroviral drug refill. A total of 1517 participants were involved in the study, however 79.8% (1210) respondents accepted to take cervical cancer screening. The study was carried out in an urban health care, so findings from rural slums are not put into consideration.⁴⁵

A cross-sectional descriptive study was done in the districts of Namacurra and Inhassunge, Mozambique, to ascertain willingness of women to be screened for cervical cancer. Women aged 30–56 years, non-pregnant were included in the study. A total of 101 (51 from Inhassunge and 50 from Namacurra) respondent participated in the study. At the end of the interview, the majority (84%) of women were willing to undergo cervical cancer screening. All 51 (100%) women who were interviewed in Inhassunge agreed to be screened. This contrasted sharply with only 34 (68%) women accepting in Namacurra. In Inhassunge, women primarily indicated that they would accept the screening because ‘it is for my health’. Reaction to the same offer was met with more suspicion and distrust in Namacurra. This study has a relatively small sample size of 101, which can reduce the power of the study and increase the margin of error.⁴⁶

2.4 FACTORS AFFECTING UPTAKE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted involving 235 women of reproductive age (15-49 years) attending immunization clinic at Central Hospital Benin City. Finding from the study showed that employment status, marital status, parity, were the only factors influencing cervical cancer screening uptake. The limitation of this study is that the findings were based on self-report as it was not possible to validate claims made by respondents in the course of questionnaire administration.³⁷

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Mater Misericordiae Hospital, Ebonyi, Nigeria, to determine the willingness as well as the factors that determines the uptake of cervical cancer screening among women. The subjects consisted of 360 women of reproductive age group and postmenopausal women, who attended the antenatal and gynecological clinics of the hospital for consultation. From the study, lack of awareness, non-availability of screening centers locally, cost and time were the main reasons adduced by respondents for not being screened. This study has a relatively small sample size of 360, which is capable of reducing the power of the study and increasing the margin of error. However, the study captures both women in their reproductive age as well as the postmenopausal women, which is more encompassing.⁴⁷

A facility based cross-sectional study in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. The sample included all 322 HIV infected women above age of 17 years and coming for chronic HIV care in public health institutions of Addis Ababa. The study showed that 24.8 % were accepted to take the screening. The factors significantly associated with acceptance of screening were educational level, source of information, awareness for the test and preventability of the disease.⁴⁸

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 STUDY AREA

This study was carried out in the surrounding areas of University of Benin main campus in Ugbowo, Ovia North-East Local Government Area, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. Ovia North East LGA is a local government area in Edo State with its administrative headquarters in the town of Okada.

The University of Benin is a federal tertiary institution founded in the year 1970. It offers both undergraduate and postgraduate studies in area of discipline that cuts across science, medical science, art, law, education, engineering, agriculture etc. The University has fifteen Faculties, one College and three Institutes.

The University of Benin main campus is situated between latitudes 60 22' 30'' – 60 25' 30'' North of the Equator and longitudes 50 35' 31'' – 50 38' 33'' East of the Greenwich along Lagos – Sagamu Expressway in Benin City.

The University of Benin is bounded in the north by Ekosodin community, in the east by Ikpoba River, in the south by Osasogie Community and the western side is Ugbowo which is also one of the host communities. It covers an area of 2,301km square.

3.2 STUDY DESIGN

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used for this study.

3.3 STUDY POPULATION

The study was carried out among female lecturers between the age of 25 years and 65 years, in line with the National Cancer Institute guidelines for cervical cancer screening ⁴⁹, in the University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State.

3.4 SELECTION CRITERIA

3.4.1 Inclusion criteria

Female lecturers between the age of 25 years and 65 years who are available at the time of the study.

3.4.2 Exclusion criteria

Female lecturers who are unavailable at the time of the study due to illness or any other reason.

3.5 DURATION OF THE STUDY

The study was carried out within a 1-year period from April, 2022 – May, 2023.

3.6 SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

This was calculated using the Cochran's formula for descriptive study.⁵⁰

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2} \quad \text{where,}$$

n = minimum sample size

z = standard normal deviation

= 1.96 at 95% confidence interval

p = prevalence rate of a particular characteristics of the target population

q = 1-p

d = degree of precision set at 0.05

p was taken as the prevalence (37.5%) of female lecturers at the University of Maiduguri who had screened for cervical cancer.⁵¹

Substituting the above in the equation;

$$n = 1.96^2 \times 0.375 \times 0.625 = 0.90$$

$$0.90/0.05^2 = 360$$

$$n = 360$$

Non-response was accounted for by adding 10.0% of the sample size to the questionnaire.

$$nf = n/1 - nr$$

where;

nf = final sample size

n = minimum sample size

nr = Non response of 10%

$nf = 360 / 1 - 0.1$

$nf = 360 / 0.9 = 400$

Therefore, the sample size (nf) = 400.

3.7 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Respondents were selected using multi-stage sampling technique involving three (3) stages.

STAGE ONE: Selection of Campus

A simple random sampling was done using a coin toss to determine the campus between Ekehuan and Ugbowo campuses of the University of Benin.

STAGE TWO: Selection of Faculties

A list of fifteen faculties (15) was retrieved from the University Brochure. They include: Faculty of Arts, Faculty of Agriculture, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Faculty of Dentistry, Faculty of Education, Faculty of Engineering, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Faculty of Law, Faculty of Life Science, Faculty of Management Science, Faculty of Pharmacy, Faculty of Physical Science, Faculty of Social Science, School of Medical Sciences, College of Medicine. Twelve (12) faculties were selected using simple random sampling by balloting.

STAGE THREE: Selection of Departments

From the selected Faculties, four (4) departments each were selected using simple random sampling technique by balloting. A total population study was carried out on all the female lecturers in the selected departments.

3.8 DATA MANAGEMENT

3.8.1 METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Data was collected using a self-administered questionnaire with open and close ended questions.

3.8.1.1 QUANTITATIVE TOOL

Data was collected using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was modified by the author using information from literature reviews and previous studies on knowledge, attitude and acceptability of cervical cancer screening.

The questionnaire had four sections: Section A contained questions that assessed the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, Section B contained questions to assess the level of knowledge of cervical cancer and cervical cancer screening among the respondents, Section C contained questions assessing the attitude of respondents towards cervical cancer screening and Section D contained questions assessing the uptake and acceptability of cervical cancer screening and factors affecting the level of acceptability.

3.8.2 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The filled questionnaires were thoroughly checked for any inconsistencies. Data coding and cleaning was done. Data was entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for the International Business Machines Corporation Social Science (IBM SPSS) version 25.0 software with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$ and 95% confidence interval. Categorical data was presented as frequencies and proportions. Continuous data was presented as means and standard deviations. Univariate analysis was done to assess the distribution of the variables. Bivariate analysis was done to determine association between respondents' socio-demographic characteristics and their level of acceptability of cervical cancer screening as well as their knowledge of cervical cancer and cervical cancer screening using chi-squared test.

3.8.3 SCORING

SOCIODEMOGRAPHICS

AGE:

Age of respondents was grouped into the following categories;

20 – 29 years, 30 – 39 years, 40 – 49 years, 50 – 59 years and 60 – 69 years.

KNOWLEDGE:

The knowledge was assessed in two domains: Good and Poor.

A total of 10 questions were used to assess the knowledge of respondents about cervical cancer screening. A score of 1 was given to each correct answer and a score of 0 was given to each wrong answer, making a maximum score of 10. The score for knowledge was converted to percentages

such that scores between 0 – 49.9% were regarded as poor knowledge, while scores of 50% and above were regarded as good knowledge. Good knowledge was coded as 1 and poor knowledge was coded as 0.

ATTITUDE:

The attitude was assessed in three domains: Very satisfactory, satisfactory, not satisfactory.

A total of 9 questions were used to assess the attitude of respondents towards cervical cancer screening. Those who agreed with the correct attitude were given a score of 2, those who were not sure of the correct attitude were given a score of 1, while those who disagreed with the correct attitude were given a score of 0. This yielded a total score of 18. The score for attitude was converted to percentages such that scores between 0 – 33.3% were regarded as not satisfactory attitude, scores between 33.4% to 66.7% were regarded as satisfactory attitude while scores of 66.8% and above were regarded as very satisfactory attitude. Very satisfactory attitude was coded as 3, satisfactory attitude was coded as 2 and unsatisfactory attitude was coded as 1.

ACCEPTABILITY:

The acceptability was assessed in two domains: Good and Poor.

A total of 4 questions were used to assess the acceptability of cervical cancer screening among respondents. A score of 1 was given for good acceptability, while a score of 0 was given for poor acceptability, making a maximum score of 4. The score for acceptability was converted to percentages such that scores between 0 – 49.9% were regarded as poor acceptability, while scores

of 50% and above were regarded as good acceptability. Good acceptability was coded as 1 and poor acceptability was coded as 0.

3.9. DATA PRESENTATION

Results of data analysis was presented using prose and frequency tables.

3.10. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The study was carried out under the supervision of a Consultant in Department of Community Health, University of Benin/University of Benin Teaching Hospital. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethics and Research Committee in UBTH. Informed consent was obtained from respondents and participants' confidentiality and privacy was maintained. The respondents were informed that they had the right to withdraw from the interview at any time and that withdrawal poses no loss or harm.

3.11. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Data collected from the respondents may be subject to recall bias; however, this was avoided using time lines to aid recall.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

TABLE 1: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Age group (in years)		
20 – 29	14	3.8
30 – 39	136	36.8
40 – 49	163	44.1
50 – 59	55	14.9
60 – 69	2	0.5
Mean ± SD	41.1 ± 7.2	
Marital status		
Married	310	83.8
Single	35	9.5
Widowed	19	5.1
Separated	4	1.1
Divorced	2	0.5
Type of marriage (n = 310)		
Monogamous	308	98.7
Polygamous	4	1.3
Religion		
Christianity	348	94.1
Islam	22	5.9
Ethnic group		
Benin	85	23.0
Esan	60	16.2
Afemai	56	15.1
Igbo	46	12.4
Yoruba	34	9.3
Urhobo	26	7.1
Isoko	18	4.9
Ijaw	16	4.3
Itsekiri	8	2.2
Idoma	9	2.4
Ebira	8	2.2
Others*	4	1.1

*Ibibio, Ikwerre

Almost half (44.1%) of the respondents were within the age group of 40 and 49 years. Majority (83.8%) of the respondents were married and almost all (98.7%) the married respondents were in monogamous marriages. 94.1% of the respondents were Christians with 5.9% being Muslims.

Ethnicity of respondents was diverse, with almost one-quarter (23.0%) being of Benin descent, 16.2% being Esan, 15.1% being Afemai, 12.4% Igbo and the rest being Yoruba, Urhobo, Isoko, Ijaw etc etc.

TABLE 2: FACULTY OF RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Faculty		
Education	72	19.5
Arts	46	12.4
Social Sciences	39	10.6
Basic Medical Sciences	34	9.2
Management Sciences	33	8.9
Life sciences	30	8.1
Physical sciences	30	8.1
Medicine	23	6.2
Law	22	5.9
Pharmacy	20	5.4
Agric	16	4.3
Engineering	5	1.4

Respondents from several faculties were interviewed. Almost one-fifth (19.5%) of them were from the faculty of Education. 12.4% were from the faculty of Arts, 10.6% from Social sciences and the rest from Basic Medical Sciences, Management Sciences, Life Sciences, Physical Sciences, Law, Medicine, Pharmacy, Agric and Engineering.

TABLE 3A: DEPARTMENT OF RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Departments		
Educational management	20	5.4
Adult education	20	5.4
Curriculum technology	16	4.3
Human Kinetics	16	4.3
Fine & Applied Arts	15	4.1
English & Literature	13	3.5
Business Administration	11	3.0
Political science	11	3.0
Computer science	11	3.0
Philosophy & Religion	10	2.7
Nursing	10	2.7
Medical Laboratory science	10	2.7
Banking & Finance	10	2.7
Sociology & Anthropology	10	2.7
Social works	10	2.7
Biochemistry	9	2.4
ISD*	8	2.2
AEB*	8	2.2
Economics & Statistics	8	2.2
Chemistry	8	2.2
Plant biology	7	1.9
Physiology	7	1.9
Medical biochemistry	7	1.9
Internal medicine	7	1.9
Accounting	6	1.6
Marketing	6	1.6
Optometry	6	1.6
Geology	6	1.6
Ophthalmology	6	1.6
Public law	6	1.6
Property law	6	1.6
Pharmacology	6	1.6
Mathematics	5	1.4
Pathology	5	1.4
Family medicine	5	1.4
Jurisprudence	5	1.4
Business Law	5	1.4
Pharmaceutical MCB*	5	1.4

*International studies and diplomacy, Animal and Environmental biology, Microbiology

TABLE 3B: DEPARTMENT OF RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Departments		
Pharmaceutical chemistry	5	1.4
Agricultural economics	5	1.4
Pharmacology & Toxicology	4	1.1
Animal science	4	1.1
Fisheries	4	1.1
Crop science	3	0.8
Electrical & Electronics engineering	2	0.5
Civil engineering	1	0.3
Computer engineering	1	0.3
Chemical engineering	1	0.3

Female lecturers from a total of 48 departments were interviewed in this study. Some of the faculties include Adult Education, Sociology & Anthropology, English and literature, Nursing, Accounting, Biochemistry, Computer Science, Internal Medicine, Public Law, Pharmacology, Animal Science, Civil Engineering.

TABLE 4A: KNOWLEDGE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Awareness of cervical cancer		
Yes	370	100.0
Source of information*		
Doctors	342	92.4
Other health workers	240	64.9
Media	177	47.8
Internet	128	34.6
Books	54	14.6
Friends	41	11.1
Family	26	7.0
Knowledge of the primary cause of cervical cancer		
Yes	208	56.2
No	162	43.8
Cause of cervical cancer (n = 208)		
Human papilloma virus	206	99.0
Prolonged use of IUCD	2	1.0
Cervical cancer is sexually transmitted		
Yes	124	33.5
No	82	22.1
I don't know	164	44.3
Symptoms of cervical cancer*		
Foul smelling vaginal discharge	340	91.9
Bleeding after sexual intercourse	240	64.9
Intermenstrual bleeding	165	44.6
Back pain	18	4.9
I don't know	11	3.0

*Multiple responses

TABLE 4B: KNOWLEDGE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Risk factors for cervical cancer*		
Multiple sexual partners	322	87.0
Early sexual debut	249	67.3
Smoking	197	53.2
Sexually transmitted diseases	162	43.8
Family history	91	24.6
I don't know	15	4.1
Poor hygiene	9	2.4
Poor diet	7	1.9
Cervical cancer can be detected early		
Yes	368	99.5
I don't know	2	0.5
Knowledge of cervical cancer screening		
Yes	368	99.5
No	2	0.5
Source of information*		
Doctors	346	93.5
Other healthcare workers	246	66.5
Media	148	40.0
Internet	122	33.0
Books	48	13.0
Family	34	9.2
Friends	34	9.2
Type of screening test		
Pap smear	366	98.9
HPV test	93	25.1
VIA	71	19.2
I don't know any	4	1.1

*Multiple responses

All the respondents had heard about cervical cancer. 92.4% of them heard about it from Doctors, 64.9% from other health workers, 47.8% from the media, 34.6% from the internet, 14.6% from books. Only 11.1% and 7.0% had heard about it from friends and family respectively.

One-third (33.5%) believed cervical cancer was sexually transmitted, almost half (44.3%) of them did not know, while 22.1% believed it was not. 91.9% of them knew that cervical cancer can cause foul smelling vaginal discharge, 64.9% knew it can cause post coital bleeding, 44.6% knew it can cause intermenstrual bleeding. However, only 4.9% knew it can cause back pain. 3.0% of them did not know any symptom of cervical cancer.

87.0% of respondents knew that multiple sexual partners is a risk factor for cervical cancer, 67.3% knew that early coitarche is a risk factor. 2.4% and 1.9% wrongly believed that poor hygiene and poor diet are risk factors for cervical cancer while 4.1% did not know any risk factor for cervical cancer.

Almost all (99.5%) of the respondents believed that cervical cancer can be detected early. Almost all (99.5%) of them had heard about cervical cancer screening and 93.5% heard about it from doctors, 66.5% from other healthcare workers, 40.0% from the media, 33.0% from the internet. Only 13.0% learnt about it from books, while 9.2% learnt about it from family and friends.

Almost all (98.9%) the respondents knew about pap smear, meanwhile only one-quarter (25.1%) knew about Human Papillomavirus testing, while 19.2% knew about Visual inspection with acetic acid. 1.1% of respondents did not know any screening test.

TABLE 4C: KNOWLEDGE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Early detection of cervical cancer improves the chances of survival		
Yes	369	99.7
I don't know	1	0.3
Commencement of cervical cancer screening		
Once a woman is sexually active	275	74.3
I don't know	91	24.6
When a woman is still a virgin	3	0.8
When a woman is no longer a virgin	1	0.3
Regularity of screening		
I don't know	158	42.7
Once in three to five years	131	35.4
Once in two years	47	12.7
Once a year	34	9.2

Almost all (99.7%) of the respondents knew that early detection can improve chances of survival, about three-quarter (74.3%) knew that cervical cancer screening should commence once a woman is sexually active however about one-quarter (24.6%) had no idea. Almost half (42.7%) of them did not know how often screening for cervical cancer should be done while a little above one-third (35.4%) knew that it should be done once in three to five years

TABLE 5: ATTITUDE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

ATTITUDE	AGREE n (%)	DISAGREE n (%)	NOT SURE n (%)
Cervical cancer is deadly if not screened and treated	368 (99.5)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.5)
Cervical cancer can be gotten through unsafe sexual practices	170 (45.9)	3 (0.8)	197 (53.2)
Any woman can get cervical cancer	331 (89.5)	3 (0.8)	36 (9.7)
People should go for checkup even if they are feeling well	367 (99.2)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.5)
Cervical cancer cannot be cured if one already has it	17 (4.6)	223 (60.3)	130 (35.1)
Screening can help in preventing cervical cancer	311 (84.1)	2 (0.5)	57 (15.4)
It is helpful to detect cervical cancer early	368 (99.5)	0 (0.0)	2 (0.5)
Screening for cervical cancer causes no harm	179 (48.4)	5 (1.4)	186 (50.3)
Screening for cervical cancer is not expensive	134 (36.2)	12 (3.2)	224 (60.5)

Almost all (99.5%) agreed that cervical cancer is a deadly disease if not screened and treated, a little over half (53.2%) were not sure if it can be gotten from unsafe sexual practices, however, 45.9% agreed that it can be gotten from unsafe sexual practices. 89.5% agreed that any woman is at risk of getting cervical cancer. Almost all of them (99.2%) agreed that people should routinely go for screening despite not having symptoms.

Almost two-thirds (60.3%) of respondents disagreed that cervical cancer cannot be cured while about one-third (35.1%) were not sure. Majority (84.1%) agreed that screening can help in preventing cervical cancer while 15.4% were not sure. Almost all (99.5%) agreed that detecting cervical cancer early is helpful. Half (50.3%) were not sure if screening for cervical cancer causes harm while almost half (48.4%) agreed that it causes no harm. 60.5% were not sure if cervical cancer screening is expensive, while a little above one-third (36.2%) agreed that it was not expensive.

TABLE 6: UPTAKE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Screened for cervical cancer		
Yes	136	36.8
No	234	63.2
Type of screening test (n = 136)		
Pap smear	128	94.1
VIA	8	5.9
Intends to continue receiving regular screenings in the future (n = 136)		
Yes	127	93.4
No	9	6.6
Reason for not wanting to continue receiving regular screenings in the future (n = 9)		
Had total hysterectomy	4	44.5
Bad experience the first time	3	33.3
No longer at risk	2	22.2

Only 36.8% of respondents had screened for cervical cancer while 63.2% had not screened. Out of the respondents who had screened, almost all (94.1%) did the pap smear while only 5.9% did the visual inspection with acetic acid. 6.6% of the respondents who had screened did not intend to continue screening for cervical cancer, as just below half (44.5%) claimed to have had a hysterectomy, one-third (33.3%) said they had a bad experience the previous times they screened while 22.2% believed they were no longer at risk of having cervical cancer.

TABLE 7: ACCEPTABILITY OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 234)	PERCENT
Intent to screen for cervical cancer		
Yes	147	62.8
No	87	37.2
Preferred cervical cancer screening method (n = 147)		
Not sure	108	73.5
Pap smear	34	23.1
Blood test	3	2.0
HPV test	2	1.4
Reasons for not wanting to screen for cervical cancer (n = 87)		
I'm not at risk	27	31.0
Too much exposure	21	24.1
Never thought of it	15	17.3
Fear	7	8.1
The process is discomfoting	6	6.9
I'm not properly informed	5	5.7
Religious reasons	5	5.7
No time	1	1.2
Negative experiences with healthcare providers/facilities that might cause hesitation to undergo screening		
Yes	109	29.5
No	261	70.5
Will screen for cervical cancer if screening is free		
Yes	286	77.3
No	84	22.7
Will screen for cervical cancer if screening causes no harm		
Yes	290	78.4
No	80	21.6

Out of the respondents who had not screened for cervical cancer, almost two-thirds (62.8%) intend to screen, and almost majority (73.5%) were not sure the type of screening test they prefer while

about one-quarter (23.1%) preferred pap smear. Out of the 37.2% who did not intend to screen, about one-third of them (31.0%) believed they were not at risk of having cervical cancer, 24.1% were worried about having to expose themselves, 8.1% said they were scared, 6.9% said the process was discomforting, 5.7% also did not think they were properly informed about the procedure, 5.7% had reservations because of religion while 1.2% of them said they did not have time.

29.5% of the respondents have had negative experiences with healthcare providers that might make them hesitant to undergo screening. Majority (77.3%) of them will undergo screening if it is free and majority (78.4%) will undergo screening if they were sure it causes no harm.

TABLE 8: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND ACCEPTABILITY OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG RESPONDENTS

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (n = 370)	PERCENT
Knowledge of cervical cancer screening among respondents		
Good	173	46.8
Poor	197	53.2
Attitude of respondents towards cervical cancer screening		
Very satisfactory	356	96.2
Satisfactory	14	3.8
Unsatisfactory	0	0.0
Overall attitude towards cervical cancer screening		
Positive	370	100.0
Negative	0	0.0
Acceptability of cervical cancer screening among respondents		
Good	290	78.4
Poor	80	21.6

Only 46.8% of respondents had good knowledge about cervical cancer while 53.2% had poor knowledge. 96.2% of them had very satisfactory attitude towards cervical cancer screening, 3.8% had satisfactory attitude, while none of them had unsatisfactory attitude. Acceptability of cervical cancer screening was good (78.4%)

TABLE 9: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KNOWLEDGE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING.

VARIABLES	KNOWLEDGE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING		χ^2	p-value
	GOOD FREQ (%)	POOR FREQ (%)		
Age group (years)				
20 – 29	4 (28.6)	10 (71.4)		
30 – 39	49 (36.0)	87 (64.0)		
40 – 49	88 (54.0)	75 (46.0)	16.2	0.003
50 – 59	32 (58.2)	23 (41.8)		
60 – 69	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)		
Marital status				
Married	152 (49.0)	158 (51.0)		
Single	9 (25.7)	26 (74.3)		
Widowed	10 (52.6)	9 (47.4)	8.9	0.063
Separated	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)		
Divorced	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)		
Type of marriage				
Monogamous	150 (48.7)	158 (51.3)		
Polygamous	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	0.1	0.959
Religion				
Christianity	165 (47.4)	183 (52.6)		
Islam	8 (36.4)	14 (63.6)	2.7	0.257
Faculty				
Social Sciences	43 (29.9)	101 (70.1)		
Medical sciences	75 (97.4)	2 (2.6)		
Arts	27 (39.7)	41 (60.3)	102.8	0.001
Life Sciences	14 (30.4)	32 (69.6)		
Physical Sciences	14 (40.0)	21 (60.0)		

Over half (58.2%) of respondents aged 50 to 59 had good knowledge about cervical cancer screening while none (0.0%) of the respondents aged 60 to 69 had good knowledge. The relationship between age and knowledge of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.003$).

Majority (74.3%) of respondents who were single had poor knowledge about cervical cancer screening while all (100.0%) of respondents who were married had poor knowledge about cervical cancer screening. The relationship between marital status and knowledge of cervical cancer screening was however not statistically significant ($p = 0.063$).

Only about half (48.7%) of respondents in monogamous marriages had good knowledge about cervical cancer screening while the other half (51.3%) had poor knowledge about cervical cancer screening. The relationship between type of marriage and knowledge of cervical cancer screening was not statistically significant ($p = 0.959$).

A little below half (47.4%) of respondents who were Christians had good knowledge about cervical cancer screening, while only about one-third (36.4%) of Muslims had good knowledge of cervical cancer screening. The relationship between religion and knowledge of cervical cancer screening was not statistically significant ($p = 0.257$).

Almost all (97.4%) of the respondents in the Medical sciences had good knowledge about cervical cancer screening while majority (70.1%) of those in the Social sciences had poor knowledge. The relationship between faculty of respondents and knowledge of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.001$).

TABLE 10: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

VARIABLES	ATTITUDE TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING		χ^2	p-value
	VERY SATISFACT ORY FREQ (%)	SATISFACT ORY FREQ (%)		
Age group (years)				
20 – 29	14 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
30 – 39	128 (94.1)	8 (5.9)		
40 – 49	160 (98.2)	3 (1.8)	4.4	0.356
50 – 59	52 (94.5)	3 (5.5)		
60 – 69	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Marital status				
Married	303 (97.7)	7 (2.3)		
Single	29 (82.9)	6 (17.1)		
Widowed	18 (94.7)	1 (5.3)	19.4	0.002
Separated	4 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Divorced	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Type of marriage				
Monogamous	301 (97.7)	7 (2.3)		
Polygamous	2 (50.0)	2 (50.0)	32.1	0.001
Religion				
Christianity	336 (96.6)	12 (3.4)		
Islam	20 (90.9)	2 (9.1)	2.1	0.359
Faculty				
Social Sciences	137 (95.1)	7 (4.9)		
Medical sciences	76 (98.7)	1 (1.3)		
Arts	67 (98.5)	1 (1.5)	4.1	0.397
Life Sciences	43 (93.5)	3 (6.5)		
Physical Sciences	33 (94.3)	2 (5.7)		

Most (98.2%) of the respondents aged 40 to 49 had very satisfactory attitude about cervical cancer screening. The relationship between age and attitude towards cervical cancer screening was however not statistically significant ($p = 0.356$).

Most (97.7%) of the respondents who were married had very satisfactory attitude about cervical cancer screening. The relationship between marital status and attitude towards cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.002$).

Only half (50.0%) of the respondents in polygamous marriages had very satisfactory attitude about cervical cancer screening while the other half (50.0%) had satisfactory knowledge about cervical cancer screening. The relationship between type of marriage and attitude towards cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.001$).

Most (96.6%) of the respondents who were Christians had very satisfactory attitude about cervical cancer screening. The relationship between religion and attitude towards cervical cancer screening was not statistically significant ($p = 0.359$).

Almost all (98.7%) of the respondents in the Medical sciences had very satisfactory attitude towards cervical cancer screening. Almost all (95.1%) of those in the Social sciences also had very satisfactory attitude. The relationship between faculty of respondents and attitude towards cervical cancer screening was however not statistically significant ($p = 0.397$)

TABLE 11: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE OF RESPONDENTS AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

VARIABLES	ATTITUDE TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING		χ^2	p-value
	VERY SATISFACT ORY FREQ (%)	SATISFACT ORY FREQ (%)		
Knowledge				
Good	172 (99.4)	1 (0.6)	9.2	0.002
Poor	184 (93.4)	13 (6.6)		

Almost all (99.4%) of the respondents who had good knowledge of cervical cancer screening also had very satisfactory attitude towards cervical cancer screening. The relationship between knowledge of cervical cancer screening and attitude towards cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.002$).

TABLE 12: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND UPTAKE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

VARIABLES	UPTAKE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING		χ^2	p-value
	YES	NO		
	FREQ (%)	FREQ (%)		
Age group				
20 – 29	1 (7.1)	13 (92.9)		
30 – 39	29 (21.3)	107 (78.7)		
40 – 49	75 (46.0)	88 (54.0)	34.7	0.010
50 – 59	29 (52.7)	26 (47.3)		
60 – 69	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Marital status				
Married	120 (38.7)	190 (61.3)		
Single	4 (11.4)	31 (88.6)		
Widowed	11 (57.9)	8 (42.1)	15.2	0.030
Separated	1 (25.0)	3 (75.0)		
Divorced	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)		
Type of marriage				
Monogamous	120 (39.0)	188 (61.0)		
Polygamous	0 (0.0)	4 (100.0)	2.5	0.112
Religion				
Christianity	133 (38.2)	215 (61.8)		
Islam	3 (13.6)	19 (83.4)	8.7	0.013
Faculty				
Social sciences	39 (27.1)	105 (72.9)		
Medical sciences	45 (58.4)	32 (41.6)		
Arts	26 (38.2)	42 (61.8)	22.2	0.020
Life Sciences	15 (32.6)	31 (67.4)		
Physical Sciences	11 (31.4)	24 (68.6)		

All (100.0%) the respondents aged 60 to 69 had screened for cervical cancer, while almost all (92.9%) of respondents aged 20 to 29 had not screened for cervical cancer. The relationship between age and uptake of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.010$).

Majority (88.6%) of the respondents who were single had not screened for cervical cancer and all (100.0%) the respondents who were divorced had not screened for cervical cancer. The relationship between marital status of respondents and uptake of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.030$).

All (100.0%) the respondents in polygamous marriages had not yet screened for cervical cancer, while 39.0% of those in monogamous marriages had screened for cervical cancer. The relationship between type of marriage of respondents and uptake of cervical cancer screening was not statistically significant ($p = 0.112$).

Almost all (90.9%) of the respondents who practiced Islam had not screened for cervical cancer, while over one-third (38.2%) of the respondents who practiced Christianity had screened for cervical cancer. The relationship between religion of respondents and uptake of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.013$).

Over half (58.4%) of the respondents in the Medical sciences had screened for cervical cancer while majority (72.9%) of those in the Social sciences had not yet screened. The relationship between faculty of respondents and uptake of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.020$).

TABLE 13: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF RESPONDENTS AND UPTAKE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

VARIABLES	UPTAKE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING		χ^2	p-value
	YES FREQ (%)	NO FREQ (%)		
Knowledge				
Good	112 (64.7)	61 (35.3)	109.1	0.001
Poor	24 (12.2)	173 (87.8)		
Attitude				
Very satisfactory	134 (37.6)	222 (62.4)	3.2	0.076
Satisfactory	2 (14.3)	12 (85.7)		

Almost two-thirds (64.7%) of the respondents with good knowledge of cervical cancer screening had screened for cervical cancer, while only 12.2% of those with poor knowledge of cervical cancer had screened. The relationship between knowledge of cervical cancer screening and uptake of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.001$).

Almost two-thirds (62.4%) of respondents with very satisfactory attitude towards cervical cancer screening had not undergone screening. The relationship between attitude towards cervical cancer screening and uptake of cervical cancer screening was not statistically significant ($p = 0.076$).

TABLE 14: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND ACCEPTABILITY OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

VARIABLES	ACCEPTABILITY OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING		χ^2	p-value
	GOOD	POOR		
	FREQ (%)	FREQ (%)		
Age group (years)				
20 – 29	4 (28.6)	10 (71.4)		
30 – 39	99 (72.8)	37 (27.2)		
40 – 49	145 (89.0)	18 (11.0)	41.1	0.000
50 – 59	42 (76.4)	13 (23.6)		
60 – 69	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)		
Marital status				
Married	255 (82.3)	55 (17.7)		
Single	16 (45.7)	19 (54.3)		
Widowed	13 (68.4)	6 (31.6)	27.6	0.002
Separated	4 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Divorced	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Type of marriage				
Monogamous	254 (82.5)	54 (17.5)		
Polygamous	1 (25.0)	3 (75.0)	8.7	0.004
Religion				
Christianity	283 (81.3)	65 (18.7)	32.9	0.001
Islam	7 (31.8)	15 (68.2)		
Faculty				
Social sciences	110 (76.4)	35 (23.6)		
Medical sciences	69 (89.6)	8 (10.4)		
Arts	48 (70.6)	20 (29.4)	9.99	0.040
Life Sciences	38 (82.6)	8 (17.4)		
Physical Sciences	25 (71.4)	10 (28.6)		

Only 28.6% of respondents aged 20 to 29 had good acceptability of cervical cancer screening while all (100.0%) of those aged 60 to 69 had poor acceptability of cervical cancer screening. The relationship between age of respondents and acceptability of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.000$).

Majority (82.3%) of respondents who were married had good acceptability of cervical cancer screening while above half (54.3%) of those who were single had poor acceptability of cervical cancer screening. The relationship between marital status of respondents and acceptability of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.002$).

Majority (75.0%) of respondents in polygamous marriages had poor acceptability of cervical cancer screening while only 17.5% of those in monogamous marriages had poor acceptability of cervical cancer screening. The relationship between type of marriage of respondents and acceptability of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.004$).

Over two-thirds (68.2%) of respondents who were Muslim had poor acceptability of cervical cancer screening while majority (81.3%) of respondents who were Christians had good acceptability of cervical cancer screening. The relationship between religion of respondents and acceptability of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.001$).

Majority (89.6%) of the respondents in the Medical Sciences had good acceptability of cervical cancer screening, while almost one-third (29.4%) of those in Arts had poor acceptability of cervical cancer screening. The relationship between faculty of respondents and acceptability of cervical cancer screening was statistically significant ($p = 0.040$).

TABLE 15: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF RESPONDENTS AND ACCEPTABILITY OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

VARIABLES	ACCEPTABILITY OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING		χ^2	p-value
	GOOD FREQ (%)	POOR FREQ (%)		
Knowledge				
Good	141 (81.5)	32 (18.5)	1.9	0.210
Poor	149 (75.65)	48 (24.4)		
Attitude				
Very satisfactory	281 (78.9)	75 (21.1)	1.7	0.192
Satisfactory	9 (64.3)	5 (35.7)		

Majority (81.5%) of respondents with good knowledge also had good acceptability of cervical cancer screening. Majority (78.9%) of those with very satisfactory attitude towards screening also had good acceptability of cervical cancer screening. The relationship between both knowledge and attitude of cervical cancer screening, and acceptability of cervical cancer screening was not statistically significant ($p = 0.210$ and 0.192 respectively).

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

Results from this study showed that majority of the respondents were married in monogamous settings and practiced Christianity. The predominant religion was not surprising as the study was carried out in the Southern part of Nigeria where Christianity is mostly practiced.

All the respondents were aware of cervical cancer, and 99.5% had knowledge of cervical cancer screening. This result is expected given that the study was conducted amongst respondents who had attained tertiary level of education. This level of education enables an individual to gain access to relevant information and resources about diverse subjects, including cervical cancer and its screening modalities. Cervical cancer is largely preventable through regular screening and early detection and adequate knowledge about screening methods enables individuals to seek timely screenings and detect pre-cancerous changes early. Early detection significantly improves treatment outcomes and reduces mortality rates. This high level of awareness about cervical cancer reported is at variance with a previous study conducted among market women in Zaria state, Nigeria, which showed that less than half of the respondents (44.3%) have heard about cervical cancer screening.⁵² This may be linked to low level of education in the respondents in the previous study which might have limited their access to information.

Majority (93.5%) of the respondents from this study heard about cervical cancer screening from doctors. This may be attributed to the fact that a higher level of education promotes good health seeking behavior. Many of these lecturers are covered by health insurance programs, which leads to better health-seeking behavior without the fear of cost, and hence, regular hospital visits and

interaction with doctors. A study which recorded similar findings was carried out among female secondary school teachers in Lagos Nigeria where doctors were the primary source of information about cervical cancer screening.⁵³

Most (97%) of the respondents knew at least one symptom of cervical cancer. This good knowledge of the symptoms of cervical cancer is contrary to findings from a study carried out among women residing in an urban slum in Lagos, South West Nigeria where majority of the women knew nothing about the symptoms of cervical cancer.⁵⁴ This contrast may be due to average educational level of the respondents in the different studies and their access to information.

Pap smear was the most popular (98.9%) screening test among respondents and only 25.1% of them knew about HPV testing as a method of screening for cervical cancer. This was not surprising considering that the Pap smear screening test has been in existence since 1941 and is by far the most popular cervical cancer screening method. The importance of the awareness of cervical cancer screening cannot be overemphasized as cervical cancer has a long precancerous phase and as such, it can be detected early and can therefore ultimately reduce the rate of mortality associated with the deadly disease. Similar findings were recorded in a study carried out among staff and students in a University in the Niger Delta where Pap smear was the most known cervical cancer screening test.⁵⁵

Most of the female lecturers correctly believed that early detection of cervical cancer increases the chances of survival and that screening should commence when a woman becomes sexually active. This poses a good picture for the efficient control of cervical cancer. However, despite good knowledge about the time of onset of cervical cancer screening, only 35.4% knew that screenings were conducted once every three years. This is similar to a study conducted among women in

Somolu Local Government Area, Lagos, Nigeria, where most of the respondents believed that screening enhances early detection and control of the disease but did not have good knowledge on the regularity of screening.⁵⁶

From this study, more than half (55.7%) of respondents knew about HPV as a cause of cervical cancer. The overall knowledge about cervical cancer and cervical cancer screening was also poor, as only 46.8% of respondents had correct knowledge. This reflects the dearth of information regarding cervical cancer in Nigeria, even among enlightened individuals. This is concerning because with a poor overall knowledge about cervical cancer even among enlightened individuals, it is expected that there will be a much poorer level of knowledge among less educated individuals. The federal government, in cooperation with doctors, the media, other health workers should ensure proper and effective dissemination about not just cervical cancer, but also the primary cause, the risk factors and the screening schedule. This can be achieved by organizing regular radio and television programs for sensitization and encouraging medical doctors to educate their patients on cervical cancer and its screening modalities regardless of their diagnosis and what they're being managed for. The increased prevalence of cervical cancer in developing countries relative to developed countries has been linked, in part, to a lack of awareness as similar patterns of knowledge were observed in a study carried out in Gabon where the overall knowledge was poor.⁵⁷

From this study, there was a significant relationship between the faculty of respondents and knowledge about cervical cancer screening. Majority (97.4%) of respondents in the Medical sciences (Basic Medical Sciences, Pharmacy, Medicine & Surgery) had good knowledge about cervical cancer screening. This is not surprising as these individuals are either doctors, or in close

proximity with doctors and therefore have access to firsthand information about cervical cancer screening.

The attitude of the respondents towards cervical cancer screening was also assessed. A very high proportion (96.2%) of the respondents had very satisfactory attitude towards cervical cancer screening. This finding can be attributed to the high level of education of the respondents interviewed. This is in consonance with a study carried out among women in Hossana Town, Hadiya zone, Southern Ethiopia, where most of the respondents had positive attitude towards cervical cancer screening.⁵⁸ Most of the respondents in this study believed that screening enhances early detection of cervical cancer. A study conducted among undergraduate female students in University of Gondar, Northwest Ethiopia in which most of the respondents agreed that early detection of the disease is important for prevention of cervical cancer corroborated this finding.⁵⁹

In this study, less than half (45.9%) of the respondents agreed that the disease can be gotten through unsafe sexual practices, which is different from a study carried out in Imo State, Nigeria in which majority of the respondents (70.6%) did not agree that unsafe sexual practices increased the chances of contacting cervical cancer.⁶⁰

Despite good awareness of cervical cancer, and positive attitude towards cervical cancer screening among the respondents, only 36.8% had screened for cervical cancer. This low uptake was attributed to some of them believing they were not at risk, time constraint, and fear of embarrassment, inadequate knowledge about the process, religious concerns. Cervical cancer screening is an invasive procedure which can be uncomfortable and may cause embarrassment or anxiety for some individuals. Non uptake of cervical cancer screening can lead to delayed diagnosis, delayed institution of treatment and consequently increased mortality associated with

the disease. The level of uptake of cervical cancer screening can be improved among this population by assuring them of privacy, allowing female health professionals carry out the screening processes, and thoroughly explaining to them what to expect. This finding was similar to findings from a study carried out in among female lecturers at the University of Maiduguri which showed that only 37.5% of participants had been screened for cervical cancer.⁶¹

From this study, there was a statistically significant association between the overall knowledge of cervical cancer screening and uptake of screening as majority (87.8%) of respondents with poor knowledge had not screened while almost two-thirds (64.7%) of respondents with good overall knowledge had screened for cervical cancer. This is expected as individuals with good overall knowledge of the cause, risk factors, screening schedule are more likely to undergo screening. This is however in contrast with a study done in Saudi Arabia which showed that only 26.2% of respondents who had knowledge of cervical cancer had been screened previously.⁶²

This study revealed that majority (78.2%) of the respondents had a high level of acceptability of cervical cancer screening. This can be attributed to their positive attitude towards screening, as majority (78.9%) of those with very satisfactory attitude also had good acceptability of cervical cancer screening, although the association was not statistically significant. This is encouraging, as willingness is an important component of behavior change and this should therefore be encouraged by listening to, understanding and providing solutions to their concerns regarding cervical cancer screening. This finding was in tandem with the findings from a study conducted among HIV positive Nigerian women, which also showed a high level of cervical cancer screening acceptance rate (79.8%).⁶³

CONCLUSION

Although almost all the female lecturers in the University of Benin were aware of cervical cancer screening, only about half of them had good overall knowledge about cervical cancer and its screening. With the high incidence of cervical cancer in developing countries, there ought to be adequate knowledge about the disease especially among lecturers as they are important in transmitting the knowledge to less enlightened individuals.

Majority of the female lecturers in the University of Benin had very satisfactory attitude towards cervical cancer screening. This poses a good picture for the effective control of cervical cancer and their likelihood of participating in regular screenings, therefore, increasing the chances of detecting precancerous lesions at an early stage.

The Uptake of cervical cancer screening among female lecturers in the University of Benin was observed to be poor, despite the positive attitude due to several factors that have been highlighted.

There was good acceptability of cervical cancer screening which implies that individuals are more likely to adhere to recommended screening guidelines and undergo screenings at the appropriate intervals to allow for timely treatment and intervention.

RECOMMENDATIONS

TO THE FEDERAL GOVERNMENT

Awareness programs that ensure dissemination of accurate, concise and clear information should be organized by the federal government.

The federal government should reinforce the positive attitude towards cervical cancer screening among female lecturers in the University of Benin by acknowledging their concerns about the invasiveness of cervical cancer screening and therefore allaying their anxiety about exposing themselves. This can be done by employing more female healthcare workers to perform the procedure.

TO THE SCHOOL AUTHORITY

The school authority should collaborate with healthcare providers to offer on-campus cervical cancer screening programs exclusively for female lecturers. Regular screening days should be scheduled to make it convenient for them to participate.

TO THE FEMALE LECTURERS

The lecturers should follow the recommended guidelines for screenings and make them a priority in their healthcare routine.

REFERENCES

1. Bruni L, Barrionuevo-Rosas L, Albero. Human Papillomavirus and related diseases report NIGERIA. 2017. Available at <http://www.hpvcentre.net/statistics/reports/NGA.pdf> [Accessed 23rd October 2021]
2. Agboola A. Textbook of obstetrics and gynecology for medical students: Cervical cancer. 2nd Ed. Nigeria: Heinemann Educational Books Plc; 2006. p.166-167.
3. Arbyn M, Weiderpass E, Bruni L, de Sanjosé S, Saraiya M, Ferlay J, Bray F. Estimates of incidence and mortality of cervical cancer in 2018: a worldwide analysis. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2020;8(2):191-203. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(19\)30482-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(19)30482-6)
4. Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Dikshit R, Eser S, Mathers C, Rebelo M, Parkin DM, Forman D, Bray F. Cancer incidence and mortality worldwide: Sources, methods and major patterns in GLOBOCAN 2012. *Int J Cancer*. 2015;136:359–386.
5. Bray F, Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Siegel RL, Torre LA, Jemal A. Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin*. 2018; 68(6):394–424.
6. Eze JN, Umeora OU, Obuna JA, Egwuatu VE, Ejikeme BN. Cervical cancer awareness and cervical screening uptake at the Mater Misericordiae Hospital, Afikpo, Southeast Nigeria. *Annals of African Medicine*. 2012; 11(4): 238–243.
7. Bisi-Onyemaechi AI, Chikani UN, Nduagubam O. Reducing incidence of cervical cancer: Knowledge and attitude of caregivers in Nigerian city to human papillomavirus vaccination. *Infect Agent Cancer*. 2018;13(1):29. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13027-018-0202-9>

8. International Agency for Cancer Research/World Health Organization. Nigeria factsheet: Globocan. 2018. Available at <https://gco.iarc.fr/today/data/factsheets/populations/566-nigeria-fact-sheets.html> [Accessed 19th October 2021]
9. Brian RW, Nicki RC, Stuart HR, Ian DP. Davidson's principles and practice of medicine: Cervical cancer. 22nd Ed. London: Elsevier Limited; 2014. p.281.
10. Ermel A, Qadadri B, Tong Y. Invasive cervical cancers in the United States, Botswana and Kenya: HPV type distribution and health policy implications. *Infect Agents Cancer*. 2016;11. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186.13027-016-0102-9>
11. Ash M, Steven D. Gynaecology by Ten Teachers: Cervical cancer. 19th Ed. Florida: CRC Press; 2011. p.130.
12. Šarenac T, Mikov M. Cervical cancer: Different treatments and importance of bile acids as therapeutic agents in this disease. *Front Pharmacol*. 2019;10:484.
13. World Health Organization. Human papillomavirus and cervical cancer. Available at [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/human-papillomavirus-\(hpv\)-and-cervical-cancer](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/human-papillomavirus-(hpv)-and-cervical-cancer). [Accessed 19th October 2021]
14. Koliopoulos G, Nyaga VN, Santesso N, Bryant A, Martin-Hirsc P, Mustafa RA, Schünemann H, Paraskevidis E. Cytology versus HPV testing for cervical cancer screening in the general population: The Cochrane database of systematic reviews. 2017;8(8):8587. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD008587.pub2>
15. Centre for Disease Control. Cervical cancer statistics. Available at <https://www.cdc.gov/cancer/cervical/statistics/index.html> [Accessed 19th October 2021]

16. Ndikom CM, Ofi BA, Awareness, perception and factors affecting utilization of cervical cancer screening services among women in Ibadan Nigeria: a qualitative study reproductive health. 2012;9(11).
17. Dim CC. Towards improving cervical cancer screening in Nigeria: A review of the basics of cervical neoplasm and cytology. Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice. 2012;15(3):247-252.
18. Eze JN, Umeora OU, Obuna JA, Egwuatu VE, Ejikeme BN. Cervical cancer awareness and cervical screening uptake at the Mater Misericordiae Hospital, Afikpo, Southeast Nigeria: Annals of African Medicine. 2012;11(4):238–243.
19. Arulogun OS, Maxwell OO. Perception and utilization of cervical cancer screening services among female nurses in University College Hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria: Pan African Medical Journal. 2012;69(11):258.
20. Nwozor CM, Oragudosi AL. Awareness and Uptake of Cervical Cancer Screening among Women in Onitsha, South-East, Nigeria. Greener journal of medical Sciences. 2013;3(8):283–288.
21. Brisson M. Impact of HPV vaccine and cervical screening on cervical cancer elimination: A comparative modelling analysis in 78 low-income and lower-middle-income countries. The Lancet. 2020;395(10224):575-590. Available at [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30068-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30068-4)
22. Centre for Disease Control. Human Papillomavirus (HPV) Vaccination: What Everyone Should Know. Available at <https://www.cdc.gov/vaccines/vpd/hpv/public/index.html> [Accessed 19th October 2021]

23. Patel C, Brotherton JM, Pillsbury A, Jayasinghe S, Donovan B, Macartney K, Marshall H. The impact of 10 years of human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination in Australia: what additional disease burden will a nonavalent vaccine prevent. *Euro surveillance*. 2015;23(41):1700737. Available at <https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2018.23.41.1700737>
24. American Cancer Society. *Cancer prevention and early detection facts and figures*: American Cancer Society. 2019 Available at <https://www.cancer.org/cancer/cervical-cancer/detection-diagnosis-staging/cervical-cancer-screening-guidelines.html>
25. Ilevbare OE, Adegoke AA, Adelowo CM. Drivers of cervical cancer screening uptake in Ibadan, Nigeria. *Heliyon*. 2020; 6(3):3505. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03505>
26. World Bank. Nigeria releases new report on poverty and inequality in country” Available at <https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/lsm/brief/nigeria-releases-new-report-on-poverty-and-inequality-in-country> [Accessed 19th October 2021]
27. Aregbeshola BS, Khan SM. Out-of-pocket payments, catastrophic health expenditure and poverty among households in Nigeria. *Int J Health Policy Management*. 2018; 7(9): 798-806. Available at <https://doi.org/10.15171/ijhpm.2018.19>
28. Nwobodo H, Ba-Break M. Analysis of the Determinants of Low Cervical Cancer Screening Uptake Among Nigerian Women. *Journal of Public Health in Africa*. 2015; 6(2):484. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4081/jphia.2015.484>
29. Igwilo AI, Igwilo UU, Hassan F, Idanwekhai M, Igbinomwanhia O, Popoola AO. The knowledge, attitude and practice of the prevention of cancer of the cervix in Okada Community. *Asian Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2012;4(3):95-98.

30. Jacobson G, Chuang L and Pankow M. Improving quality of care and timely access to radiation therapy for patients with invasive cervical cancer at the National Cancer Institute Paraguay. *Gynecol Oncol Rep.* 2018; 25:82–86.
31. Torre LA, Islami F, Siegel RL, Ward EM and Jemal A. Global cancer in women: Burden and trends. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2017; 26:444–457.
32. Thomson C, Foreman D. Cancer survival in England and the influence of early diagnosis: What can we learn from recent EURO CARE results? *Br J Cancer.* 2009;101(2):102-109. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.bjc.6605399>
33. Bazile J, Rigodon J, Berman L. Intergenerational impact of maternal mortality: Qualitative findings from rural Malawi. *Reprod Health.* 2015;12(1) Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-4755-12-S1-S1>
34. Pande RP, Ogwang S, Karuga R. Continuing with “....a heavy heart” – Consequences of maternal death in rural kenya. *Reprod Health.* 2015;12(2) Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-4755-12-S1-S12>
35. Kes A, Ogwang S, Pande RP. The economic burden of maternal mortality on households: evidence from three sub-counties in rural western kenya. *Reprod Health.* 2015; 12(3) Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/1742-4755-12-S1-S3>
36. Tadesse S. Socioeconomic and cultural vulnerabilities to cervical cancer and challenges faced by patients attending care at Tikur Anbessa Hospital: A cross-sectional and qualitative study. *BMC Women’s Health.* 2015;15(75) Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-015-0231-0>

37. Obi AI. Cervical cancer knowledge and screening practices among women of reproductive age in Benin City, Edo State. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*. 2015; 27(2):59-66.
38. Ugonma WD, Bagbi LE, Chidozie JN, Gregory NI, Chiagoziem OE, Amarachi JA, Uchechukwu MC, Ikechukwu ND. Knowledge, attitude and perception on cervical cancer screening among women attending ante-natal clinic in Owerri west L.G.A, South-Eastern Nigeria: A cross-sectional study. *Cancer Treatment and Research Communications*. 2021; 28: 2468-2942. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctarc.2021.100392>.
39. Mengesha A, Messele A, Beletew B. Knowledge and attitude towards cervical cancer among reproductive age group women in Gondar town, North West Ethiopia. *BMC Public Health*. 2020; 20(209). Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-8229-4>
40. Tokuc B, Eren F, Saraçoğlu GV. Knowledge, Attitudes and Practice about Cervical Cancer Screening among Women Living in Edirne: Burcu Tokuc. *European Journal of Public Health*. 2017; 27(3). Available at <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckx186.178>
41. Ibekwe RU. Comparative assessment of knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer and its screening among clinical students in southern Nigeria. *Nigerian Health Journal*. 2015; 15(2).
42. Ahmed SA, Sabitu K, Idris SH, Ahmed R. Knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer screening among market women in Zaria, Nigeria. *Niger Med J*. 2013;54(5): 316-319. Available at <https://doi.org/10.4103/0300-1652.122337>
43. Heena H, Durrani S, AlFayyad I, Riaz M, Tabasim R, Parvez G, Abu-Shaheen A. Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices towards Cervical Cancer and Screening amongst

Female Healthcare Professionals: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Journal of Oncology*. 2019; 2019(5423130) Available at <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/5423130>

44. Ehwarieme AT, Ekrebe AJ. Knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer screening among female undergraduates residing in halls of residence, University of Benin. *University of Benin Journal of Science and Technology*. 2017;5(1). Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335172826> KNOWLEDGE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES RESIDING IN HALLS OF RESIDENCE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN INTRODUCTION *University of Benin Journal of Science and Tech*
45. Ezechi CC, Gab-Okafor CV, Ostergren PO, Pettersson KO. Willingness and acceptability of cervical cancer screening among HIV positive Nigerian women. *BMC Public Health*. 2013;13(1). Available at: <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2458-13-46>
46. Carolyn MA, Carla SM, Meridith B, Aventina C, Troy DM, Mohsin S. Health Education Research. 2012;27(3):544–551. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cys008>
47. Eze JN, Umeora OU, Obuna JA, Egwuatu VE, Ejikeme BN. Cervical cancer awareness and cervical screening uptake at the Mater Misericordiae Hospital, Afikpo, Southeast Nigeria. *Ann Afr*. 2012;11:238-43. Available at: <https://www.annalsafmed.org/text.asp?2012/11/4/238/102856>
48. Belete N, Tsige Y, Mellie H. Willingness and acceptability of cervical cancer screening among women living with HIV/AIDS in Addis Ababa. *Gynecologic Oncology Research and Practice*. 2015;2(1):47–49. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4881166/>

49. Fontham ET. Cervical cancer screening for individuals at average risk: 2020 guideline. *A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*. 2020;70(5) 321-346. Available at <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21628>
50. Cochran WG. Sampling Techniques, 3rd Edition. New York. John Willey and Sons Inc. 1977.
51. Maigari, Inuwa B, Muhammad A, Keveer R. Attitude And Practice Of Cervical Cancer Screening Among Female Lecturers In University Of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. *Journal Of Public Health*. 2015;1(3). Available at <https://researchjournali.com/view.php?id=1485>
52. Ahmed S, Sabitu K, Idris S, Ahmed R. Knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer screening among market women in Zaria, Nigeria. *Niger Med J*. 2013;54(5):316-9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4103/0300-1652.122337> [Accessed 20th May 2023]
53. Surakatu O, Onyeodi I, Balogun M. Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Cervical Cancer Screening among Female Teachers in an Urban Community in Lagos, Nigeria: Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Cervical Cancer Screening. *Nigerian Medical Journal*, 2013;63(3):236–247. Available at: <https://nigerianmedjournal.org/index.php/nmj/article/view/112> [Accessed 20th May 2023]
54. Olubodun T, Odukoya O, Balogun MR. Knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer prevention among women residing in an urban slum in Lagos, South West Nigeria. *Pan African Medical Journal*. 2019; 32 (130):1937-8688. Available at <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2019.32.130.14432> [Accessed 21st May 2023]
55. Owoeye OG, Ibrahim IO. Knowledge and Attitude towards cervical screening among female staff and students in a tertiary institution in the Niger Delta. *International*

- Journal of Medicine and Biomedical Research*. 2013;2(1). Available at doi.org/10.14194/ijmbr.219 [Accessed 21st May 2023]
56. Amu E, Ndugba S, Olatona F. Cervical Cancer Screening Uptake and Barriers to Screening among Females in Somolu, South Western Nigeria. *Journal of Community. Medicine & Health Care*. 2017;2(3):1-4. Available at <https://ir.unilag.edu.ng/handle/123456789/9228> [Accessed 21st May 2023]
57. Assoumou S, Mabika M, Mbiguino N, Mouallif M, Ennaji I. Awareness and Knowledge regarding cervical cancer, Pap smear screening and human papillomavirus among Gabonese women. *BMC women's health*. 2015; 15(37). Available at <http://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-015-01932-2> [Accessed 22nd May 2023]
58. Aweke Y, Ayanto Samuel Ersado T. Knowledge, attitude and practice for cervical cancer prevention and control among women of childbearing age in Hossana Town, Hadiya zone, Southern Ethiopia: Community-based cross-sectional study. *Public Library of Science*. 2017;12(7):1-18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0181415> [Accessed 21st May 2023]
59. Getaneh A, Tegene B, Belachew T. Knowledge, attitude and practices on cervical cancer screening among undergraduate female students in University of Gondar, Northwest Ethiopia: an institution based cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health* 21, 2021 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-10853-2> [Accessed 21st May 2023]
60. Dozie U, Nwadi C, Umunakwe C, Asuzu N, Obikonu I, Dozie I. Knowledge and Attitude towards Cervical Cancer: A Case Study of Undergraduate Students in Imo State, Nigeria. *Open Access Library Journal*, 2020;7(.6). Available at <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1106441> [Accessed 21st May 2023]

61. Maigari, Inuwa B, Muhammad A, Keвер R. Attitude And Practice Of Cervical Cancer Screening Among Female Lecturers In University Of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. *Journal Of Public Health*. 2015;1(3). Available at <https://researchjournali.com/view.php?id=1485> [Accessed 21st May 2023]
62. Heena H, Durrani S, AlFayyad I, Riaz M, Tabasim R, Parvez G, et al,. Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices towards Cervical Cancer and Screening amongst Female Healthcare Professionals: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Journal of Oncology*. 2019; 5423130:1687-8450 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/5423130> [Accessed 21st May 2023]
63. Ezechi O, Gab-Okafor C, Ostergren P, Pettersson K. Willingness and acceptability of cervical cancer screening among HIV positive Nigerian women. *BMC Public Health*. 2013;13(16) Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-13-46> [Accessed 21st May 2023]

APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND ACCEPTABILITY OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AMONG FEMALE LECTURERS IN THE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN.

Dear respondent,

We are final year medical students carrying out a one-year project which is designed to assess knowledge, attitude and acceptability of cervical cancer screening among female lecturers. All information given will be treated as confidential. Your participation is voluntary. Thank you.

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

1. Age as at last birthday _____
2. Marital Status: Single Married Separated Divorced Widowed Cohabiting
3. Type of marriage: Monogamous Polygamous
4. Ethnic group: _____
5. Religion: Christianity Islam African Traditional Religion Others (specify): _____
6. Faculty: _____
7. Department: _____

SECTION B: KNOWLEDGE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

8. Have you ever heard of cancer of the cervix? Yes No
9. What is your source of information? (**Multiple response**) Media Friends Family Doctors Other health care workers Books Internet Others (specify) _____
10. Do you know the primary cause of cervical cancer? Yes No . If Yes go to question 11, if No go to question 12.
11. What is the cause of cervical cancer? Human papilloma virus Curse from the village Prolonged use of IUCD Having gonorrhoea Internet Church others (specify) _____
12. Cervical cancer is sexually transmitted. Yes No I don't know
13. What are the symptoms of cervical cancer? (**Multiple response**) Foul smelling vaginal discharge Intermenstrual bleeding Bleeding after sexual intercourse Back pain I don't know
14. What are the risk factors for cervical cancer? (**Multiple response**) Multiple sexual partners Early sexual debut Sexually transmitted diseases Family history of cervical cancer Poor hygiene Smoking Poor diet I don't know
15. Can Cervical cancer be detected early? Yes No I don't know
16. Have you ever heard of cervical cancer screening? Yes No . If Yes go to question 17, if No go to question 18.

17. What is your source of information? Media Friends Family Doctors Other health care workers Books Internet Others (specify) _____
18. Which cervical screening test do you know? Pap smear Visual inspection with acetic acid Human Papilloma virus (HPV) test I don't know any others (specify) _____
19. Early detection of cervical cancer improves the chances of survival Yes No I don't know
20. When should cervical cancer screening commence? Once a woman is sexually active When a woman is still a virgin When a woman is no longer sexually active I don't know
21. How often should cervical cancer screening be done? Once a year Once in two years Once in three to five years Once in four years I don't know

SECTION C: ATTITUDE TOWARDS CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

S/N		Agree	Not sure	Disagree
22.	Cervical cancer is a deadly disease if not screened and treated			
23.	Cervical cancer is a disease that can be gotten through unsafe sexual practices			
24.	Any woman can get cervical cancer			
25.	People should routinely go to a health care provider for check-up even though they're feeling well			
26.	Cervical cancer cannot be cured if one already has it			
27.	Screening can help in preventing cervical cancer			
28.	It is helpful to detect cervical cancer early			
29.	Screening for cervical cancer causes no harm to women			
30.	Screening for cervical cancer is not expensive			

SECTION D: ACCEPTABILITY AND UPTAKE OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING

31. Have you ever been screened for cervical cancer? Yes No . If yes go to 32, if No go to 33
32. Which method of cervical cancer screening did you do? Pap smear Visual inspection with acetic acid Blood test Human papilloma virus test Not sure others (specify) _____
33. Do you intend to screen for cervical cancer? Yes No . If yes go to 34, if No go to 35.
34. Which type of cervical cancer screening would you prefer? Pap smear Visual inspection with acetic acid Blood test Human papilloma virus test Not sure others (specify) _____
35. What is/are your reason(s) for not wanting to be screened for cervical cancer? (**Multiple response**) Fear I'm not at risk Cost Husband will not allow No time Never thought of it others (specify) _____
36. Have you ever had any negative experiences with healthcare providers or facilities that might make you hesitant to undergo cervical cancer screening? Yes No
37. Will you screen for cervical cancer if screening is free? Yes No
38. Will you screen for cervical cancer if screening causes no harm? Yes No
39. Will you continue receiving regular cervical cancer screenings in the future? Yes No